

Effect of Computer Animation Instructional Strategies on Academic Achievement of Students in Computer Graphics in Secondary Schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State

ANIH, Anselem Anayochukwu (Ph.D)¹ & OBADIARU Itohonsa Obadiru (Ph.D)²

^{1&2}Department of Science Education,
Faculty of Education,
Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State

anihaa@fuotuoche.edu.ng

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of computer animation instructional strategies on academic achievement of students in computer graphics in secondary schools in Ogbia L.G.A. of Bayelsa State. Two research questions guided the study and three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level. Quasi-experimental research design with a pre-test post-test non-equivalent approach was adopted for this study. The target population comprised 1811 SS II students in 34 secondary schools in Ogbia LGA, with a purposive random sampling technique used to select a sample size of 306 SS II students. This sample consisted of 164 SS II students in the experimental group (85 male and 79 female) and 142 SS II students in the control group. Data collection utilized a teacher-made test known as the "Computer Graphics Achievement Test (CGAT)," whose validity was established through face and content validation. The instrument's reliability was assessed using the Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-20) formula, yielding a reliability index of .82. The research involved administering the CGAT as a pre-test to both the experimental and control groups before implementing computer animation instructional strategies. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was applied to test the hypotheses. The study's findings showed that students taught computer graphics using computer animation outperformed those subjected to the lecture method. Also, male students outperformed the female students when taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies. In view of the findings, the study recommended that curriculum planners should revise the curriculum in order to incorporate computer animation as a core teaching method for computer graphics.

Keywords: Computer Animation Instruction, Academic Achievement, Computer Graphics, Secondary School Students

Introduction

Computer graphics is the field of study that focuses on the creation, manipulation, and representation of visual images using computers. Computer graphics generally means creation, storage and manipulation of models and images. Such models come from diverse and expanding set of fields including physical, mathematical, artistic, biological, and even conceptual (abstract) structures. It involves a variety of techniques and applications, including image processing, visualization, and rendering, to produce graphics for diverse industries such as entertainment, design, and scientific research (Foley, van Dam, Feiner, & Hughes, 2015). Computer graphics is concerned with producing images and animations (or sequences of images) using a computer. This includes the hardware and software systems used to make these images. The effective teaching of

computer graphics often involves a combination of creative and critical thinking, visualization, hands-on, technology-enhanced, and inquiry-based approaches. Connecting abstract concepts to real-world applications and adapting instruction to diverse learning styles can contribute to a more engaging and comprehensive learning experience for students. Therefore, there is need for a proper teaching method of computer graphics.

A teaching method refers to the approach or structured plan used by educators to facilitate learning. It includes the techniques, tools, and activities designed to challenge and engage students. These methods can differ greatly depending on the subject, learning goals, student characteristics, and educational setting. According to Bamidele and Yoade (2017), traditional teaching still predominantly follows a conservative model where teachers act as the primary source of knowledge and students as passive recipients. The lecture method, a specific teaching approach, involves the instructor delivering information verbally to a large group, with students primarily listening and taking notes. Incorporating computer animation into the lecture method leverages technology to enhance the learning experience.

Computer animation has been traditionally defined as inanimate entities that appear to take on dynamic attributes such as motion and growth which are normally associated with living organisms (Ploatzne & Lowe, 2012). Computer animation is the process of creating moving images using computer graphics. It involves generating animated sequences by manipulating digital models and environments to simulate motion and dynamics. Basak, Yucehan and Ahmet (2018), described computer animation as an effective learning tool that attracts attention, engages learner, and sustains motivation and enhance retention of concepts that results in meaningful learning. According to Pekdag (2010), computer animations involve animating graphics in specific scenarios and should be seen as alternative methods for visualizing knowledge. However, Akor (2011) pointed out that the use of computer animation in classrooms aims to engage students' interest, motivate them to learn, and foster independent responsibility for education, higher-order thinking skills, and creativity in problem-solving.

Additionally, well-designed computer animations can facilitate faster and easier learning for students and serve as valuable tools for teachers in explaining complex subjects. It has been shown from several research reports such as Kasali (2015) and Wishart (2014) that animations as technological tools used in education have contributed a lot to the students' fulfillment of cognitive function. Nwoye, Obi, Ene, and Shiaki (2019) argued that the failure of teachers to implement suitable teaching strategies significantly impacts students' academic performance in science-related subjects. They suggested that the choice of instructional methods plays a crucial role in determining how effectively students grasp scientific concepts and apply them. According to their findings, when teachers fail to select and use appropriate strategies aligned with the subject matter and students' learning needs, it can lead to lower academic achievement especially in science subjects.

Academic achievement refers to the levels of success attained by students in their educational pursuits, either through grades or test scores. Academic achievement, according to Ejesi (2014), is the outcome of education – the extent to which a student, teacher or institution have attained their educational goals. Hanushek, Rivkin and Kain (2015), defined achievement as the level of

attainment of a person in an examination, that is, how an individual is able to demonstrate his or her abilities in an examination. Academic achievement includes gaining high scores in school subjects and examination (Obiweluo, 2014). It is the outcome of education, the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals; and this is commonly measured by examinations or continuous assessment (Udim & Etim, 2016). Academic achievement is the knowledge acquired and skills developed in schools (Vein, Parveen, Syed & Nazir, 2013). Hanushek, Rivkin and Kain (2015) defined achievement as the level of attainment of a person in an examination, that is, how an individual is able to demonstrate his or her abilities in an examination.

The results by Gambari, Falode and Adegbenro (2014), indicated that the students taught mathematics using computer animation performed significantly better than their counterparts taught using lecture method respectively. Chikendu (2018), posited that instructional computer animation had significant effect on students' achievement in science subjects. According to Ugwuanyi, Okeke, Nnamani, Obochi & Obasi (2020), animated PowerPoint significantly enhanced the achievement of students in physics than the non-animated PowerPoint presentation. While the studies mentioned above focused on the effectiveness of the computer animation instructional strategy in the context of teaching mathematics and other science subjects, it is important to recognize that computer studies (computer graphics), like mathematics, is a complex and intricate subject that requires a deep understanding and effective teaching methods. Therefore, the findings of these studies may have implications for computer graphics as well, particularly in understanding potential gender differences in academic achievement related to technology-based learning tools.

Gender refers to the social, cultural, and psychological attributes, roles, behaviors, and identities that a society considers appropriate for men, women, and people of other genders, often categorized as masculine, feminine, or other identities. Chikendu (2018), posited that female students performed better than their male students taught using computer animation instructional strategies. Therefore, further studies are required to clarify the effect of different instructional strategies on academic achievement of boys and girls. It does appear that these gender differences in students' achievement vary with the method of instruction. One wonders whether the computer animation can equally be effective in teaching science subjects like Computer Studies (computer graphics) and their influence on gender. This necessitated the present study which investigated the effect of computer animation instructional strategies on academic achievement of students' in computer graphics in secondary in Ogbia LGA of Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

The quality of computer graphics education in most secondary schools in Nigeria, particularly in Ogbia LGA, Bayelsa State, appears to be rapidly declining due to poor teaching approach. This has led to consistently poor achievement in the West Africa Senior School Certificate Examinations (WASSCE). The integration of computer animation instructional strategies in secondary school education has gained prominence, yet its impact on students' academic

achievement in computer graphics remains underexplored, particularly in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Meanwhile, traditional teaching methods have failed to engage students effectively, resulting in poor understanding and low achievement in computer graphics. Despite the potential of computer animation to enhance learning by providing dynamic and interactive content, there is limited empirical evidence on its effectiveness in this context. This gap in research is critical, as it affects curriculum development and instructional practices in secondary schools. The disparity in students' academic performance in computer graphics across various schools in Bayelsa State further emphasizes the need to investigate innovative teaching strategies. Most teachers lack the necessary training and resources to implement computer animation techniques, potentially exacerbating educational inequalities. Moreover, students in Bayelsa State face unique socio-economic challenges that may influence the effectiveness of these instructional strategies. Therefore, this study investigated the effect of computer animation instructional strategies on academic achievement of students' in computer graphics in secondary in Ogbia LGA, Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of computer animation instructional strategies on academic achievement of students in computer graphics in secondary in Ogbia LGA, Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study investigated:

1. the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught computer graphics with computer animation instructional strategies (Experimental group) and those taught using lecture method (Control group) in both pre-test and post-test in public and private secondary schools in Ogbia LGA of Bayelsa State;
2. the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies (Experimental group).

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies (Experimental group) and those taught using lecture method (Control group) in both pre-test and post-test in Ogbia LGA of Bayelsa State?
2. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught computer graphics with computer animation instructional strategies (Experimental group)?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study and they were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of SS II students taught computer graphics using computer animation

instructional strategies and those taught the same topic using lecture method in both pre-test and post-test in Ogbia LGA of Bayelsa State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female SS II students taught computer graphics with computer animation instructional strategies.

Ho₃: There is no significant interaction effect of gender and methods (computer animation instructional strategies and lecture methods) on students' academic achievement in computer graphics.

Research Method

Quasi-experimental research design with a pre-test post-test non-equivalent approach was adopted for this study. Quasi-experimental research design is characterized by the absence of random assignment of subjects to experiment and control groups (Nworgu, 2015). The target population comprised 1811 SS II students, with a purposive random sampling technique used to select a sample size of 306 SS II students. This sample consisted of 164 SS II students in the experimental group (85 male and 79 female) and 142 SS II students (78 male and 64 female) in the control group. Data collection utilized a teacher-made test known as the "Computer Graphics Achievement Test (CGAT)," whose validity was established through face and content validation.

The instrument's reliability was assessed using the Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-20) formula, yielding a reliability index of .82. The research began with administering the Computer Graphics Aptitude Test (CGAT) as a pre-test to both the experimental and control groups to establish baseline data on students' prior knowledge and skills. Following this initial assessment, the researchers implemented computer animation instructional strategies within the experimental group. To ensure effective delivery of these strategies, a two-week training session was organized for the regular computer science teachers at the participating schools. This training aimed to equip the teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively integrate computer animation into their instructional practices. Mean and standard deviation were employed to address the research questions, while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was applied to test the hypotheses.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies (Experimental group) and those taught using lecture method (Control group) in both pre-test and post-test in Ogbia LGA of Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies and those taught using lecture method

Groups	Number	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	

Experimental	164	37.66	5.89	40.07	6.08	2.41
Control	142	34.82	5.61	36.01	5.98	1.19
Mean Diff.						1.22

In the study, students in the experimental group (taught using computer animation instructional strategies) had a higher pre-test mean score (37.66) compared to the control group (taught using the lecture method) with a mean score of 34.82. Post-test scores also showed the experimental group outperforming the control group, with mean scores of 40.07 and 36.01, respectively. The mean gain from pre-test to post-test was 2.41 for the experimental group and 1.19 for the control group. This resulted in a mean difference in post-test scores of 1.22 favoring the experimental group.

Research Question 2: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught computer graphics with computer animation instructional strategies (Experimental group)?

Table 2: Mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies

Groups	Number	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	
Male	85	35.71	5.82	38.62	6.01	2.91
Female	79	32.64	5.10	34.93	5.68	2.29
Mean Diff.						0.62

In the study, male students taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies had a higher pre-test mean score (35.71) compared to female students (32.64). Post-test scores also showed males outperforming females, with mean scores of 38.62 and 34.93, respectively. The mean gain from pre-test to post-test was 2.91 for male students and 2.29 for female students. The resulting mean difference in post-test scores was 0.62, favouring male students.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of SS II students taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies and those taught the same topic using lecture method in both pre-test and post-test.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance on the mean achievement scores of SS II students taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies and those taught using lecture method

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: ACHIEVEMENT					
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	68.17	1	68.17	5.56	.000
Intercept	193.80	1	193.80	7.11	.000
GROUP	201.44	1	201.44	6.05	.000
Error	5338.24	304	17.56		
Total	5801.65	306			
Corrected Total	5611.54	305			

Table 3 indicates that the computed F value of 6.05 is highly significant at a level of .00, which is lower than the predetermined .05 significance level for the study. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, suggesting a noteworthy distinction in the mean scores of students who were taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies compared to those taught using lecture method.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female SS II students taught computer graphics with computer animation instructional strategies.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance on the mean achievement scores of male and female SS II students taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies

Dependent Variable: ACHIEVEMENT					
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	30.46	1	30.46	6.30	.000
Intercept	142.61	1	142.61	8.15	.000
GENDER	26.34	1	26.34	5.67	.000
Error	1567.84	162	9.56		
Total	1767.25	164			
Corrected Total	1671.10	161			

Table 4 indicates that the computed F value is 5.67, demonstrating statistical significance at a p-value of .00. Given that this significance level of .00 is lower than the .05 set for the study, the null hypothesis is consequently rejected. This implies a noteworthy distinction in the mean scores of male and female students who were taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies.

H₀₃: There is no significant interaction effect of gender and methods (computer animation instructional strategies and lecture methods) on students' academic achievement in computer graphics.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance on the interaction effect of gender and methods (computer animation instructional strategies and lecture method) on SS II students' achievement in computer graphics

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	73.22	2	36.61	4.38	.00	
Intercept	97.05	1	97.05	8.36	.00	
Methods*Gender	56.84	1	56.84	6.11	.01	
Error	3766.56	304	12.39			Rejected
Total	3993.67	306				
Corrected Total	3652.09	305				

Table 5 shows that the calculated F value is 6.11 which is found to be significant at .01. Since this significant level (.01) is less than the .05 significant level set for the study, the null hypothesis is, accordingly, rejected. This means that there was a significant interaction effect between methods and gender in students' academic achievement scores in computer graphics.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study showed that students taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies significantly outperformed those taught through traditional lecture methods in terms of academic achievement. This suggests that the interactive and engaging nature of computer animation enhances understanding and retention of complex concepts in computer graphics. Consequently, integrating computer animation into the curriculum could lead to improved educational outcomes for students in this subject area. The finding of this study is in accordance with Njoku and Eze-Odurukwe (2015), and Ikwuka and Samuel (2017), who posited that students' academic achievements are greatly improved when taught with computer animations instructional strategies.

The finding of the study showed that male students taught computer graphics using computer animation instructional strategies outperformed their female counterparts taught same topic using computer animation instructional strategies. The finding aligns with Adigwe (2014), who posited that male students exhibit higher academic achievement in science-related subjects than their female counterparts when exposed to computer animation instructional strategies. This suggests that the use of computer animation may enhance the learning experience more effectively for male

students. Consequently, educators might consider tailoring their instructional methods to address these gender differences in academic achievement.

Conclusion

The study concludes that computer animation is a more effective instructional strategy for teaching computer graphics compared to traditional lecture methods, leading to higher student performance. Additionally, it was observed that male students achieved better outcomes than female students when taught using computer animation techniques. These findings suggest a need to explore tailored instructional approaches that address gender disparities in learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Curriculum planners should revise the curriculum to incorporate computer animation as a core teaching method for computer graphics, recognizing its effectiveness in enhancing student performance. By integrating these innovative instructional strategies, educational institutions can better equip students with the necessary skills and knowledge in this field.
2. The Bayelsa State government should organize conferences, seminars, and workshops led by relevant professional bodies to educate educators on effective computer animation instructional strategies.

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